

Radiation Hazard of Ball Lightning

Mikhail L. Shmatov

*Ioffe Institute, 194021 St. Petersburg, Russia
M.Shmatov@mail.ioffe.ru*

Abstract— The observational data corresponding to the assumption about emission of high-energy photons by ball lightning and, in particular, to the assumption about the high radiation hazard of some ball lightning are presented. The main points of the ball lightning model explaining these data are also presented. According to the model, ball lightning has a core consisting of clouds of electrons and almost totally ionized ions which oscillate with respect to each other. The possibility and expedience to check these assumptions and the model, in particular, to create ball lightning in the experiments with ordinary or rocket-triggered lightning, are considered.

Keywords— ball lightning, radiation hazard, avionics, gamma-ray glow, experiments with ordinary lightning, experiments with rocket-triggered lightning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of radiation hazard of ball lightning was the first discussed problem of radiation hazard of atmospheric electricity (see, e.g., Refs. [1–11]). The first report, corresponding to the assumption about the high radiation hazard of some ball lightning, was published in 1886 by Cowgill, who worked in U.S. Consulate in Maracaibo, Venezuela [12]. This report describes an accident that happened on the night of October 24, 1886, near Maracaibo and was accompanied by “a smoky appearance and a peculiar smell” and “a loud humming noise and a vivid, dazzling light, which brilliantly illuminated the interior of the house” [12]. A family of nine persons, sleeping in his house and awakened by the noise and light, has suffered [12]. Cowgill reported the symptoms similar to those of radiation sickness, namely, violent vomiting, falling out of head hair “upon the side which happened to be underneath when the phenomenon occurred”, swelling and formation of large black blotches on skin which on the ninth day “were transformed into virulent raw sores” [12]. He also reported that “the trees around the house showed no signs of injury until the ninth day, when they suddenly withered, almost simultaneously with the development of the sores upon the bodies of the occupants of the house” and mentioned that he had visited the sufferers who were in one of the hospitals of Maracaibo [12].

Cowgill described the accident as “a recent strange meteorological occurrence” and “an addition to the list of electrical eccentricities” [12]. Garfield was probably the first who interpreted this accident as associated with ball lightning [3]. Later, this interpretation was discussed by other authors (see, e.g., Refs. [5, 7, 10, 11]). Note that the sufferers did not report observation of a fiery ball or a similar object inside their house or near it, but this does not contradict to the assumption that they were influenced by ball lightning,

because it is possible that they could not see ball lightning due to its dazzling light and/or some other reason(s) [7, 10, 11].

The fact that Ref. [12] was published in 1886 seems to be one of the factors providing the reliability of the presented data, because that time, the falsification of the information about the aforementioned symptoms was probably impossible due to the absence of knowledge about the reported combination of the symptoms. It is worth noting that Cowgill was probably the first who described the symptoms of heavy radiation sickness.

The opinion that any ball lightning does not emit dangerous ionizing radiation also exists. For example, Stakhanov [1 (page 17)] mentioned a letter informing him about the symptoms of radiation sickness, in particular about falling out of hair and teeth, after the passage of ball lightning near the author of the letter, and considered this information as a part of a myth about ball lightning.

The check of the assumption about the radiation hazard of some ball lightning is principally important, first of all, for establishing both the physical nature of ball lightning and the real danger of ball lightning for humans and avionics. One of the ball lightning models, explaining this assumption, was proposed by the author of this paper (see, e.g., Refs. [7–11, 13–16]). Its main points are presented briefly in Section II. Several non-biological effects of ball lightning, that were described in literature and could be caused by high-energy photons from ball lightning, are described in Section III. In Section IV, the possibility to check both the assumption about radiation hazard of some ball lightning and the model under consideration by means of collection and analysis of observational data related to registration of fluxes of high-energy photons of atmospheric origin with duration of several seconds and longer is discussed. In particular, the information about the explanation of several parameters of fluxes of high-energy photons described in Refs. [17, 18] within framework of this model is presented. In Section V, the possibility to create ball lightning in the experiments with ordinary or rocket-triggered lightning is considered. It is evident that the success of such experiment would provide the possibility to check the assumption about the emission of high-energy photons by ball lightning and, in particular, about the high radiation hazard of some ball lightning directly. Some factors related to the importance of the problem of ball lightning and, as a result, to the expedience of the large-scale experimental studies devoted to its solution are also considered.

II. BALL LIGHTNING MODEL EXPLAINING THE ASSUMPTION ABOUT RADIATION HAZARD OF SOME BALL LIGHTNING

According to the model proposed by the author, ball lightning has a core consisting of clouds of electrons and almost totally ionized ions which oscillate with respect to each other and undergo the random motion disturbing the oscillatory one [7–11, 13–16]. When the core is spherically symmetrical, its particles oscillate in radial directions. Only such situations were analyzed quantitatively. The center of the core is surrounded by a practically empty region in which the electron density n_e and the ion density n_i are much less than those in another, relatively dense region of the core. The core has the positive electric charge arising due to the escape of some of the electrons from it. This charge is much less than the charge of all of the ions of the core. Therefore, at least in the dense region of the core $n_e \approx 7.262n_i$, where the factor 7.262 is the approximate average value of atomic number of the components of the air. The core is surrounded by a region called the depleted layer which almost completely isolates the core from the atmosphere and transfers the atmospheric pressure on it. The stability of the core is provided by the oscillation of its particles and the atmospheric pressure.

The parameters of the core depend strongly on the maximum value ε_{osc}^{\max} of the electron kinetic energy ε_{osc} corresponding to its oscillatory motion. In the equations describing some of the parameters of the ball lightning core, it is convenient to use the initial value $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$ of ε_{osc}^{\max} , the parameter $\gamma_{osc}^{\max} = \varepsilon_{osc}^{\max} / (mc^2) + 1$, where m is the rest mass of the electron and c is the velocity of light, and its initial value $\gamma_{osc}^{\max 1} = \varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1} / (mc^2) + 1$. The random motion of the electrons is important mainly as an effect suppressing their radiative recombination with the ions of the core at the oscillation stages corresponding to relatively low ε_{osc} . The typical kinetic energies, corresponding to the random motion of the electron and ion of the core, and the maximum value of the kinetic energy, corresponding to the oscillatory motion of any ion, are much less than ε_{osc}^{\max} .

The initial acceleration of the core is one of the stages of the formation of ball lightning and results from attraction of the electrons to the positive charge injected into the atmosphere and the effect usually called “cold runaway” or “thermal runaway” (see also Ref. [15] and Section V). These terms describe the situation when the strength of the electric field in gas or plasma is so high that the electron, influenced by this field, acquires high kinetic energy ε_k or, in other words, become runaway, at any initial value of ε_k (see, e.g., Refs. [19, 20] and bibliographies in Refs. [15, 20]). Many modes of oscillation of electron are excited initially, but the losses of energy due to the emission of radiowaves quickly attenuate almost all of them except a spherically symmetrical one and, in some situations, a few other. In situations corresponding to relatively high volume density of ball lightning energy ρ_E (we use this parameter to describe dense

regions) and long ball lightning lifetime τ_{bl} (here we do not take into account the possibility of elimination of ball lightning by ordinary lightning, collision with some obstacle, etc.), spherically symmetrical core generates photons and loses energy mainly due to bremsstrahlung and the amplitude A_e of oscillation of the electrons is much than its radius R_c . In model examples presented in Refs. [7, 15, 16], the initial values of A_e are of the order of 1 mm. The amplitude of oscillation of the ions is much less than A_e . The core is optically thin for its bremsstrahlung radiation.

At $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$ of about 50 keV and higher, the value $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max} \approx 10$ keV can be considered corresponding to the end of existence of ball lightning. For example, in the model situations considered in Ref. [14], the largest time of a decrease in ε_{osc}^{\max} from 10 keV to 1 keV is about 0.4 s, while for same ball lightning, the time of a decrease in ε_{osc}^{\max} from 50 keV to 10 keV is about 2.3 s.

The model yields that $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$ can be of the order of 10 MeV and explains the existence of ball lightning with τ_{bl} up to a few minutes and ρ_E up to about 1 kJ/cm³ and higher. Note that these values are much higher than the results of mistaken estimates of such parameters for ball lightning models without the use of the assumption about the external supply of energy from Refs. [21, 22]. The reason is that the estimate of attainable τ_{bl} , presented in Ref. [21], corresponds to the mistaken assumption that any ball lightning is optically thick for its radiation, while the estimate of attainable ρ_E , presented in Ref. [22], is based on the mistaken interpretation of virial theorem (for details, see Refs. [10, 14]).

The maximum energy of photon emitted by ball lightning is about ε_{osc}^{\max} . The average rate $d\bar{R}$ of emission of photons with energies from mc^2w to $mc^2(w+dw)$ from unit volume of the dense region of the core equals $n_i n_e S(\gamma_{osc}^{\max}, w) dw$, where $S(\gamma_{osc}^{\max}, w)$ is a function that depends only on γ_{osc}^{\max} and w . Details of calculation of $S(\gamma_{osc}^{\max}, w)$ and its plots at $\gamma_{osc}^{\max} = 5, 11$ and 21 are presented in Ref. [8] where the parameter γ_{osc}^{\max} is denoted as γ_{\max} ; see also Refs. [7, 15].

At $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$ of the order of 1–10 MeV, several tens percent of the total ball lightning energy ε_{bl} will be converted into energy of photons with energies of the order of 0.1 MeV and greater. When irradiating a human body with such photons, the ratio of the absorbed energy to the energy of the photon flux is of the order of 0.1 (see, e.g., Refs. [7, 23] and bibliography in Ref. [7]). According to Ref. [24], when irradiating a human being, a dose of 100 rad has a strong effect on blood and a dose of 400 rad results in a heavy radiation sickness and can cause death [24]. The model under consideration yields, for example, that if a human being is irradiated by photons from ball lightning with $R_c \approx 10$ cm,

$\tau_{bl} \approx 5$ s and $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1} \approx 10$ MeV during the total time of its existence and the distance d between the human being and ball lightning is fixed, doses of 100 and 400 rad correspond to d of about 25 and 13 m, respectively [7]. Note that at the chosen $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$, the parameter $\tau_{rad} = 1$ s used in Eq. (33) of Ref. [7] corresponds to $\tau_{bl} \approx 5$ s (details are presented in Refs. [8, 10, 13]). Note also that the situations when the dose is less than 100 rad even if d is of the order of several cm are also possible and according to Ref. [4], sometimes there is no apparent physiological effect at the dose of 500 rad.

The high-energy photons from ball lightning can also cause misoperation of electrical and electronic equipment, in particular avionics, and even irreversible damage to it [7, 11]. For example, at the dose of 5000 rad, corresponding to irradiation of Si, “some very sensitive electronic components have been shown to fail in slow irradiation regimes” [24]. The model under consideration yields that such irradiation is quite possible. In some situations, high-energy photons from ball lightning can cause melting of some parts of the equipment and short circuits (see Section III).

Radiation hazard of ball lightning to aircraft crews, passengers and equipment can increase due to acceleration of Compton electrons, arising due to scattering of high-energy photons from ball lightning in air, by thundercloud electric fields (see also Refs. [17, 18, 20, 25]).

III. SOME EFFECTS PRESUMABLY CAUSED BY HIGH-ENERGY PHOTONS FROM BALL LIGHTNING

Dmitriev et al. [26] have published near-fantastic, but well-documented report about ball lightning observed in Khabarovsk, USSR (now Russia) on August 24, 1978. Ball lightning had a diameter of about 1.5 m, existed during the time of about 1 minute (in the English version of Ref. [26] the information about this time is omitted) and has melted about 440 kg of ground. Probably, ball lightning also evaporated about 175 kg of water (before the influence of ball lightning the ground was wet due to a strong rain). The melted ground filled the well with the diameter of about 1.5 m and the depth of 20 to 25 cm. One of the authors of Ref. [26] observed this ball lightning himself. Dmitriev et al. [26] assumed that the ground was heated by the electromagnetic radiation with frequency in the range of $10^8 - 10^9$ Hz. Using the information about the trajectory of the ball lightning, Dmitriev et al. [26] concluded that the time τ_i of its influence on the ground had been short and estimated the power of this radiation assuming that $\tau_i = 0.1$ s. Note that “Near the place where the ball lightning burst, the vegetation covering the ground did not grow again” [26]. This information has some similarity to the aforementioned information about the trees from Ref. [12].

In Ref. [13], the data from Ref. [26] were explained within framework of ball lightning model described in Section II (see also Ref. [27] where the impossibility to explain these data within framework of some other models of ball lightning is demonstrated). According to this explanation, the ground was heated by high-energy photons [13]. The dose absorbed by the

ground was huge, namely, about 1.4×10^6 Gy = 1.4×10^8 rad. This estimate is based on the data according to which the ground was heated to the temperature of about 1700 °C and its specific heat was 840 J (kg K)⁻¹ [26].

In Ref. [28] the information about a ball lightning event accompanied by melting of small shot in the hunting cartridges with cartoon cases is presented. This melting was explained as an effect caused by heating of the lead of small shot by high-energy photons from ball lightning [27]. The influence of the ball lightning on the cartridges did not result in detonation of the mercury fulminate in their percussion caps (see Ref. [28]), while the temperature of self-ignition and explosion of this material is 130 to 150 °C [29]. This was explained as a result of relatively weak heating of mercury fulminate by high-energy photons from ball lightning due to a relatively small atomic fraction of the high-Z element, namely, mercury, in this material [27] (the chemical formula of mercury fulminate is Hg(ONC)₂ [29]).

In some situations, ball lightning causes glowing of filament of the turned-off incandescent lamp (see, e.g., Refs. [30–33]). Grigor’ev and Shiryayeva [33] tried to explain this effect as heating of the filament by electromagnetic radiation from ball lightning (they also described this radiation by the term “microwave radiation”). However, calculations presented in Ref. [33] contain the important mistakes [34]. In the situations when glowing of the filament is caused by ball lightning flying near the lamp, it can be explained as a result of heating of the filament by high-energy photons from ball lightning, while in the situations when this effect is caused by ball lightning flying near the switch, it can be explained as a result of ionization of the air in the switch by such photons.

Klass [35] mentioned “... one report of a higher-than-normal radioactivity measurement on the ground where a UFO had “landed.” The radioactivity quickly subsided as it would if produced by X-ray radiation.” This report can be interpreted as that about observation of ball lightning that was described as UFO and emitted photons with energies sufficiently high for production of the β^+ -active isotopes due to photonuclear reactions (see, e.g., Refs. [9, 17, 36]).

IV. EXPECTED USEFULNESS OF REGISTRATION OF HIGH-ENERGY PHOTONS FROM THUNDERCLOUDS FOR BALL LIGHTNING STUDIES

It is evident that more or less reproducible generation of ball lightning with the use of the laboratory equipment or/and ordinary or rocket-triggered lightning would provide establishing its nature and check of all of the assumptions about it. According to the model proposed by the author, the probability of success of the laboratory experiments is low due to the high requirements on kinetic energies and total number of accelerated electrons forming, eventually, the ball lightning core, but the experiments with the use of ordinary and rocket-triggered lightning are highly desirable. Some possible experiments of such a kind are considered in Refs. [7, 13, 15, 27] and Section V. In any case, check of this model can also result from studies of the fluxes of gamma-rays with

the duration of several seconds and longer from thunderclouds. Below, for the sake of brevity and simplicity, any such flux will be called “gamma-ray glow”, although other terminologies are also in use (see, e.g., Refs. [9, 11, 16–18, 36]). Studies of the fluxes of X-rays from thunderclouds would also be very useful (see also Ref. [14] where the model situations with relatively low $\varepsilon_{osc}^{\max 1}$ are considered, and Ref. [37], where a balloon-borne X-ray spectrometer is described), but the registration of such fluxes seems to be more difficult due to absorption of X-rays in the air.

The first attempts of registration of high-energy photons from ball lightning were undertaken more than fifty years ago [2, 5, 38, 39]. Dmitriev [2] measured a radiation dose rate from the ball lightning at a distance of about 2 m from it with a scintillation gamma radiometer. Unfortunately, either the original Russian version of Ref. [2] or its English version contains the very important erratum: in the Russian version, the value of 1.2 millirad per hour is presented, while the value presented in the English version equals 1.2 megarad per hour. This fact was discussed, in particular, in Refs. [5] and [11]. Note that the later value can be presented as about 330 rad per second and, in combination with other information published by Dmitriev [2], seems to be incompatible with his survival. In any case, Dmitriev wrote that the operation of his radiometer could be influenced by radiowaves from the ball lightning [2]. The experiments described in Refs. [5, 38, 39] were performed, in particular, in order to check one of the ball lightning models.

In recent years, the experimental studies of generation of high-energy photons due to the electrical activity of atmosphere are intensive, in particular, registration of gamma-ray glows occurs rather often (see, e.g., Refs. [17, 18, 36, 40–46]). This allows us to assume that if ball lightning really emits gamma-rays and/or X-rays, this fact will be established in the observable future. For the reliable conclusion of such a kind, the simultaneous registration of high-energy photons and visible light from ball lightning is necessary. Therefore, the experiments in which both high-energy photons and visible light are being detected (see, e.g., Refs. [18, 46]) will be especially effective. Besides, registration of visible light should provide establishing location and size of ball lightning.

According to Imyanitov [47], “even outside the thunderclouds, in the clouds ball lightning are one hundred times more frequent than near the ground”. Although the conclusion about the quantitative correctness of this statement will be possible only after the special studies, it is worth noting that it corresponds to the assumptions of the author about the favorableness of the high altitudes for both the formation of ball lightning and the realization of the relatively long τ_{bl} [14, 15]. This statement also corresponds to the relatively high probability of successful search for high-energy photons from ball lightning with the use of aircraft, balloons and unmanned aerial vehicles (see also Refs. [10, 20, 37, 40, 42, 46]).

It is quite possible that the high-energy photons from ball lightning were already detected. For example, several parameters of flux of high-energy photons, recorded by

Umemoto et al. [17] on January 13, 2012 in Niigata prefecture, Japan, were explained as those of flux of high-energy photons from ball lightning [9]. Also it has been shown that a simultaneous, 15-min-long registration of visible light (its sources looked like glowing patches which appeared and disappeared during the observation) and an increase in the rate of gamma-ray count at Aragats Space Environmental Center, Armenia, on September 1, 2020 by Chilingarian et al. [18] could be registration of visible light and gamma-rays from a swarm of ball lightning [16]. Fig. 11 in Ref. [44] may correspond to registration of photons with energies in the range of 0.15–1.5 MeV from several, for example, six, moving ball lightning. Note that this figure has some similarity to Fig. 1 in Ref. [48].

V. THE POSSIBILITY TO CREATE BALL LIGHTNING IN THE EXPERIMENTS WITH ORDINARY OR ROCKET-TRIGGERED LIGHTNING

The observational data and the model described in Section II allow us to assume that several scenarios of the injection of the positive charge into the atmosphere with the subsequent formation of ball lightning are possible [3, 10, 15].

The reports about the formation of ball lightning in situations when the ordinary lightning strikes the ungrounded antenna (see, e. g., Ref. [32 (p. 102, report No. 140)]) and the information about the equipment used in the last experiment of Professor G.-W. Richmann (see, e.g., Ref. [31]) correspond to the assumption that such injection can occur when the positive cloud-to-ground lightning strikes the ungrounded elongated conductor [7]. The geometry of the possible experiment of such a kind is shown in Fig. 1a. One of the conditions of the realization of this scenario is that all of the accelerated electrons or at least a significant fraction of them do not hit the conductor.

The formation of ball lightning at the stage of the return stroke in the regions of the propagation of both negative [13] and positive leaders seems to be possible. The neutralization and subsequent positive charging (see, e.g., Ref. [49 (Subsection 4.4.1)]) of the former region can probably create ball lightning near the points of the strike of the negative cloud-to-ground lightning or/and near the head(s) of the defunct negative leader(s) of such lightning, the formation of ball lightning may also be caused by the similar processes involved into the intracloud and cloud-to-cloud discharges.

A.A. Marvin reported about the formation of ball lightning near the sharpened end of the cable another end of which was connected to the lightning arrester placed on the geodetic landmark [6 (p. 148, report No. 117)]. The ball lightning arose when lightning struck the geodetic landmark [6]. The region of the formation of this ball lightning seems to be an analog of the neighborhood of a head of the defunct leader of a cloud-to-ground lightning. Note, however, that the sign of the ordinary lightning mentioned in the report of A.A. Marvin is not known and this report is also compatible with the assumption about the injection of the positive charge due to the hit of the positive leader in the lightning arrester with a

Fig. 1. The geometries of some possible experiments on the formation of ball lightning with the use of ordinary lightning. Thick solid lines denote conductors. Isolation of the underground part of one of the conductors in Fig. 1b is not shown.

high grounding resistance. The geometry of the experiment similar to that of A.A. Marvin is shown in Fig. 1b.

The return stroke of the negative cloud-to-ground lightning having one descending negative leader and one ascending positive leader results in the injection of the positive charge not only in the channel of the negative leader but also in that of the positive leader (see, e. g., Ref. [49 (Subsection 4.4.1)]). Thus, the return stroke supplies the additional positive charge in the channel of the ascending positive leader of the negative cloud-to-ground lightning [49] and, probably, can cause the formation of ball lightning in the region of the propagation of this leader, for example, near its head. A similar process of ball lightning formation may also occur in situations when the negative cloud-to-ground lightning has several ascending leaders [49] and when the return strokes supply the additional positive charge in the channel(s) of the positive leader(s) of the intracloud and cloud-to-cloud lightning. In order to increase the probability of formation of ball lightning during the experimental campaign, many installations shown in Fig. 1 can be used simultaneously.

Attempts to create ball lightning in the experiments with rocket-triggered lightning are described in Refs. [39, 50]. Several other possible versions of such experiments were discussed in Ref. [11], bibliography therein and in Ref. [13, 27]. Note, however, that the experiments with ordinary lightning seem to reproduce the situations in which formation of ball lightning was observed. Therefore, the probability of their success is probably higher, although the experiments with rocket-triggered lightning may also be successful.

As for the expedience of rather expensive experiments on the formation of ball lightning, which require, in particular, strict safety measures, it is worth noting that solution of the problem of ball lightning will be useful for optimization of treatment of humans influenced by ball lightning and establishing its real danger for aviation. The problem of existence of ball lightning in atmospheres of other planets is potentially important for safety of some space missions and for interpretation of some observational data that can be

obtained in the future [1, 13, 51]. Besides, the problem of ball lightning seems to be “politically” important for fusion studies: the absence of reliable explanation of this widely-known natural phenomenon, the features of which are determined by plasma effects, can be used as an argument against the statements about the ability of plasma physics community to solve in the observable future the problem of controlled thermonuclear fusion [52].

Note that the safety measures, necessary for the experiments on the formation of ball lightning, can probably be provided, in particular, in the regions where the experiments with rocket-triggered lightning are being performed (see, e.g., Refs. [50, 53]).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The published information about several biological and non-biological effects of ball lightning allows us to conclude that the assumption about the high radiation hazard of some ball lightning is valid. The ball lightning model, proposed by the author, explains this assumption and does not use the assumptions about the existence of some new particles, etc. (see, e.g., Refs. [5, 54] where the models of such a kind are presented). This model also yields, in particular, that at least some gamma-ray glows are associated with ball lightning. Check of this model in the nearest future is quite possible and expedient.

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